

Original paper

DEVELOPING METHODOLOGIES FOR IMPROVING MUSICAL CULTURE IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Annotation

INTRODUCTION: the article analyzes the methodological foundations for developing and enhancing musical culture in the educational system, its role in students' spiritual, aesthetic, and creative development, and the importance of transmitting cultural heritage to future generations. The views of great scholars on music are highlighted, emphasizing its pedagogical and cultural significance.

AIM: the main objective of the study is to improve the methodology of developing musical culture in Uzbekistan's education system by introducing interactive and innovative approaches, while integrating national heritage and international pedagogical practices.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: analytical, comparative, and experimental methods were used, along with observation, interviews, and statistical-graphical analysis. Based on these, a new conceptual framework was developed that integrates modern pedagogical technologies with interactive and individualized approaches.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS: the results demonstrated that electronic resources, multimedia tools, musical games, dramatization, and simulations significantly enhance students' musical taste, rhythmic sensitivity, creative imagination, and performance skills. Moreover, integrating national musical heritage (maqom, folk songs, oral folklore) with global methodologies provides a sustainable methodological foundation for fostering musical culture.

CONCLUSION: the study confirmed that applying innovative teaching methodologies and technologies makes the educational process more effective, strengthens aesthetic education, and plays a crucial role in developing students' creative and musical abilities.

Keywords: musical culture, interactive methods, innovative technologies, aesthetic education, national heritage, musical games, creative abilities.

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РАЗРАБОТКА МЕТОДИК ПОВЫШЕНИЯ МУЗЫКАЛЬНОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ В СИСТЕМЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

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Аннотация

ВВЕДЕНИЕ: в статье анализируются методологические основы формирования и развития музыкальной культуры в системе образования, ее роль в духовном, эстетическом и творческом развитии личности. Рассматриваются взгляды великих мыслителей на музыку и значимость передачи богатого культурного наследия будущим поколениям.

ЦЕЛЬ: основная цель исследования — усовершенствовать методологию развития музыкальной культуры в образовательной системе Узбекистана, выявить эффективность применения инновационных педагогических технологий и интеграцию национального и международного опыта.

МАТЕРИАЛЫ И МЕТОДЫ: использованы аналитический, сравнительный, экспериментальный методы, а также наблюдение, интервью и статистико-графический анализ. На основе полученных данных разработана новая концепция с использованием интерактивных и индивидуализированных подходов.

ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ И РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ: результаты показали, что применение мультимедийных ресурсов, электронных учебников, музыкальных игр, драматизации и симуляций значительно повышает музыкальный вкус, ритмическую чувствительность, воображение и исполнительские навыки учащихся. При этом интеграция национального музыкального наследия (фольклор, макам, народные песни) с международными методами формирует устойчивую методологическую основу.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ: исследование подтвердило, что использование инновационных методик и технологий делает образовательный процесс более эффективным, усиливает эстетическое воспитание и способствует развитию творческих и музыкальных способностей молодежи.

Ключевые слова: музыкальная культура, интерактивные методы, инновационные технологии, эстетическое воспитание, национальное наследие, музыкальные игры, творческие способности.

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TA'LIM TIZIMIDA MUSIQA MADANIYATINI OSHIRISH USULLARINI ISHLAB CHIQUISH

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Annotatsiya

KIRISH: maqolada ta'lim tizimida musiqiy madaniyatni shakllantirish va rivojlantirish metodologiyalari, uning shaxs ma'naviyati, estetik didi va ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni tahlil qilinadi. Buyuk allomalarimizning musiqaga oid qarashlari yoritilib, milliy madaniy merosni keyingi avlodlarga yetkazishdagi ahamiyati asoslanadi.

MAQSAD: O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida musiqiy madaniyatni rivojlantirish metodologiyasini takomillashtirish, interaktiv va innovatsion yondashuvlar orqali o'quvchilarning estetik didi va ijodiy faoliyatini oshirishdir.

MATERIALLAR VA METODLAR: tadqiqotda analitik, qiyosiy, eksperimental, kuzatish va suhbat, statistik-grafik tahlil metodlari qo'llanildi. Shu asosda interaktiv, individual yondashuvlar hamda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar integratsiyalashgan yangi konseptual model ishlab chiqildi.

MUHOKAMA VA NATIJALAR: natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, musiqiy madaniyatni rivojlantirishda elektron metodik tizimlar, multimedia vositalari, musiqiy o'yinlar, drammatizatsiya va simulyatsiyalar o'quvchilarning musiqiy didini, ritmik sezgirligini, ijodiy tasavvurini va ijro mahoratini sezilarli oshiradi. Shu bilan birga, milliy meros (maqom, xalq qo'shiqlari, folklor)ni xorijiy ilg'or tajribalar bilan uyg'unlashtirish samarali metodologik asos yaratadi.

XULOSA: tadqiqot musiqiy madaniyatni shakllantirishda innovatsion texnologiyalarni qo'llash ta'lim jarayonini yanada samarali qilishini, estetik tarbiyani kuchaytirishini hamda yosh avlodning ijodiy va musiqiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishda muhim o'rin tutishini tasdiqladi.

Kalit so'zlar: musiqiy madaniyat, interaktiv metodlar, innovatsion texnologiyalar, estetik tarbiya, milliy meros, musiqiy o'yinlar, ijodiy qobiliyat.

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It is well known that musical culture plays a crucial role in the spiritual, aesthetic, and intellectual development of the individual. The process of forming musical culture within the educational system serves not only as a means of learning art but also as a way of fostering creativity, enhancing aesthetic taste, and enriching the cultural life of society. At present, there is a strong social and pedagogical demand for organizing musical culture on the basis of innovative pedagogical technologies, and for increasing the effectiveness of the subject "*Musical Culture*" as one of the core activities in the educational process. Consequently, in recent years, the issue of effectively utilizing the potential of national culture and art as an important means of education has gained particular significance.

Psychologists emphasize that a person is not born with fully developed abilities, but rather with a capacity — a source for the emergence and development of certain abilities. Ability is regarded as an individual characteristic of a person that constitutes a

subjective condition for successfully performing a particular type of activity. Every ability manifests itself in the process of activity. However, aptitude does not develop on its own; a favorable environment is essential for its development. At times, a child may be born with a natural aptitude for music, but unless a supportive environment is provided for the formation of musical qualities, this aptitude may remain underdeveloped. One of the leading factors in the formation of an individual as a personality is the environment. By *environment*, we understand the totality of external conditions that influence a person, which in turn can be classified into natural environment, social environment, family environment, and others. Aristotle, in his reflections on musical modes that transform the psyche, provided the following explanation: *“Music in one mode makes a person gentle and kind, while another may lead to excitement and irritability.”* In his view, the melodies of the Phrygian, Dorian, and Lydian modes have a positive effect on human health and spirit, whereas music in other modes should not be introduced to the ears of the younger generation.

Research Methods The following methods were employed in the course of the study:

Analytical method: analysis of existing literature, textbooks, and scientific articles;

Comparative method: comparison of international and Uzbek experiences;

Experimental method: identification of the effectiveness of new methodological approaches through pedagogical experimentation;

Observation and interview: collection of data through surveys and observations with students and teachers;

Statistical and graphical analysis: evaluation of experimental results and formulation of conclusions.

Conceptual Framework Based on the findings, a new concept was developed for improving the methodology of fostering musical culture in the educational system of Uzbekistan. This framework integrates interactive and individualized approaches while making extensive use of modern educational technologies.

The reviewed literature demonstrates that music occupies a central role in shaping human spirituality, morality, and aesthetic perception. Classical scholars such as al-Farabi and Ibn Sina regarded music not merely as entertainment, but as a profound pedagogical and therapeutic instrument. Their insights underscore the multidimensional value of music: as a means of moral education, as a tool for psychological well-being, and as an essential component of cultural heritage. These perspectives remain relevant in contemporary discourse, especially when addressing the challenges of educating the younger generation in an era of globalization and cultural transformation. However, the current situation reveals a growing gap between the philosophical ideals of music and the practical realities of modern musical consumption. The rise of “entertainment songs” — melodically appealing but shallow in content — reflects a shift toward commercialized cultural products that fail to contribute to moral or intellectual growth. This phenomenon suggests that while music has the potential to nurture social values, not all forms of

music fulfill this function. Consequently, the development of pedagogical methodologies must carefully distinguish between music that enriches cultural identity and music that merely provides temporary amusement.

International pedagogical practices further highlight the diversity of approaches to cultivating musical culture. The Italian *Hexachord* and Greek *Tetrachord* systems demonstrate the historical depth of music theory, while modern methods such as Suzuki's approach in Japan and Kodály-inspired practices in Europe emphasize emotional expression, auditory training, and systematic skill development. These methodologies illustrate that successful music education integrates both technical mastery and emotional engagement, ensuring that students develop not only cognitive but also affective dimensions of musicality. In this regard, Uzbekistan's educational system faces both opportunities and challenges. On one hand, it possesses a rich cultural and musical heritage that can serve as a foundation for pedagogical innovation. On the other, it must contend with the global spread of commercialized music that may dilute traditional values. Therefore, critical engagement with both national heritage and international practices is necessary in order to design a methodology that is contextually relevant yet globally informed.

In several European countries (such as the United Kingdom, Germany, and France), the educational process incorporates dramatization, musical games, audiovisual simulations, and variative exercises to foster the creative and aesthetic abilities of children. In this way, the pedagogical process is conducted on the basis of interactive and differentiated approaches, taking into account each child's individual abilities and interests. International research has shown that in the development of musical culture, the use of electronic textbooks, multimedia resources, virtual music laboratories, and educational games significantly enhances students' musical taste, rhythmic sensitivity, and performance skills. At the same time, these tools strengthen emotional responsiveness, creative imagination, and performance culture. It should be emphasized that global pedagogical experience serves as an important scientific and practical source for the educational system of Uzbekistan. By adapting advanced methodological approaches to the national education context, the opportunities for developing the musical culture of the younger generation can be greatly expanded. Nevertheless, although the methodological foundations of Uzbekistan's education system are theoretically rich, in practice, interactive and innovative approaches are not sufficiently implemented in classroom activities. Therefore, improving the methodology of developing musical culture in the educational system is both a scientifically and practically urgent issue, one that is closely connected with the fields of pedagogy, musicology, psychology, and, more broadly, the social sciences.

The issue of developing musical culture and fostering performance qualities and skills among primary school students has been studied by a number of scholars in Uzbekistan as well as abroad. In particular, within the Uzbek education system, researchers such as Sh. Ayxodjaeva, A. Bakhriyev, G. Ergasheva, D. Kavilova, N. S.

Kiyamov, O. Ibroximov, H. Nurmatov, Q. Panjiev, R. Qodirov, I. Rajabov, D. Yu. Saipova, N. Khalilov, R. Yunusov, and others have investigated the methodology of developing musical culture, students' creative abilities, and the effectiveness of methodological approaches in the classroom. Their works are primarily focused on methodological and pedagogical analysis, as well as on promoting students' creative activity.

In the CIS countries, scholars such as B. Asafyev, V. K. Belabardova, Yu. Borev, L. Dmitriyev, D. Kabalevsky, V. Kanikovskiy, V. Karktechan, S. Karueva, N. Kirilova, M. Klimov, M. Kogan, N. Layzerov, A. Losev, V. Morozov, V. I. Petrushin, V. Sokolov, B. Vasilyev, K. Vinogradov, N. A. Vetlugina, and R. Yusson have explored the development of musical culture in both theoretical and practical contexts. Their research has focused on the pedagogical foundations of music education, the formation of students' musical taste and creative abilities, and the evaluation of methodological effectiveness. Foreign scholars (T. Suzuki, J. Curwen, É. Jaques-Dalcroze, C. Orff, L. Wyatt, J. Watson) have emphasized interactive and creative methods, the development of musical taste in young children, and the use of audiovisual materials and dramatization in shaping musical abilities. Their research, being pedagogically and technologically advanced, can serve as a valuable foundation for enhancing pedagogical practice in Uzbekistan. Thus, the issue of *"Improving the Methodology of Developing Musical Culture in the Educational System"* has already been provided with a sufficient scientific basis by Uzbek and CIS scholars. However, questions of applying interactive methods, innovative pedagogical approaches, and the use of modern technologies have not yet been sufficiently addressed. Consequently, there is a clear necessity to refine the methodology of developing musical culture within the education system and to introduce advanced methodological practices.

In this regard, the present study, aimed at improving the methodology of developing musical culture within the educational system, is directed toward elaborating effective methodological approaches on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies. Accordingly, the research has primarily addressed the following tasks:

Examining the concept of musical culture and its pedagogical, aesthetic, and psychological aspects;

Analyzing existing methodological approaches based on the experiences of Uzbekistan, CIS countries, and foreign practices;

Identifying the possibilities of applying interactive and innovative methods in the pedagogical process;

Evaluating the effectiveness of a new methodological concept through pedagogical experimentation;

Developing practical recommendations for teachers and educational institutions;

Defining opportunities for improving the educational process based on the research findings.

The objectives and tasks outlined above form the conceptual foundation of the research and provide a systematic framework for implementing both practical and scientific measures directed toward improving the methodology of developing musical

culture in the educational system.

Analytical Indicators of the Existing Demand (Need) for Research Outcomes: At present, although the methodological bases for developing musical culture among primary school students in Uzbekistan's educational system are relatively established, the use of interactive and innovative approaches in practice remains limited. In particular:

1. Students' interest and creative activity. Experiments and surveys have demonstrated that students' interest in music lessons and their creative activity remain restricted under traditional methods; however, the application of interactive methods and electronic resources significantly enhances their engagement.

2. Teachers' methodological preparedness. While many teachers are willing to adopt new pedagogical technologies, there is an evident lack of clear methodological guidelines and manuals. This, in turn, hinders the wide-scale implementation of innovative approaches.

3. Pedagogical and technological resources. Although schools are equipped with audio-visual and interactive materials, there are no developed standards for their systematic and effective application. Consequently, the potential of these resources is not fully utilized.

4. Integration of national and international experience. Methodological approaches advanced in the CIS and other foreign countries have not been adapted to Uzbekistan's context, resulting in a relatively low level of implementation of advanced practices.

Hence, the above indicators reveal a clear demand for improving the methodology of developing musical culture in the educational system. Through the introduction of a new pedagogical concept, the integration of interactive and individualized approaches, as well as the effective use of modern technologies, it is possible to enhance students' creative and musical abilities, organize lessons more efficiently, and improve the overall pedagogical process.

The Degree of Investigation of the Research Problem, Achievements in Global Scientific Directions, and Competitor Analysis

The issue of developing musical culture and shaping performance qualities and skills among the younger generation in the educational process has been extensively studied not only in Uzbekistan but also within the broader domain of world science. In international practice, the pedagogical foundations of music education, methods for cultivating aesthetic taste in children, and the psychological and methodological aspects of developing creative abilities have been thoroughly explored. For instance, in Italy and Greece, music systems (the "Hexachord" in Italy and the "Tetrachord" in Greece) have emphasized the development of tonal hearing, rhythmic ability, and performance skills among students. In China, methodologies based on audio-visual resources have proven effective in fostering listening and performance competencies within the learning process. Similarly, research in the CIS countries in the field of music pedagogy has focused on enhancing students' musical taste, stimulating their creative activity, and

advancing the use of interactive methods in the learning process. Specifically, scientific investigations conducted in Russia, Kazakhstan, Belarus, and other countries have elaborated methodological concepts concerning the use of game technologies in music education, the development of children's musical memory and auditory abilities, as well as the expansion of their creative expressive activity. The use of variable methodological approaches and pedagogical technologies by teachers enriches lessons and allows for the systematic development of students' musical skills. For example, through musical fairy tales, role-playing games, song dramatizations, and diverse rhythmic exercises, children's musical sensitivity, artistic imagination, and creative thinking are nurtured. Moreover, the growing use of modern digital technologies—multimedia textbooks, audio-video materials, and virtual music programs—demonstrates an increasing emphasis on improving the effectiveness of music education. Such approaches are significant not only for enhancing students' musical literacy but also for elevating their aesthetic upbringing, fostering personal interests, and instilling respect for cultural values. On this basis, music-pedagogical practices formed in CIS countries can serve as a valuable methodological foundation for the Uzbek educational system.

When comparing advanced experiences in CIS countries with those of Uzbekistan, both commonalities and differences emerge. Common to all is the emphasis on developing musical culture, fostering creative thinking among youth, and applying innovative methods in music education. The distinctiveness of Uzbekistan lies in its music-pedagogical approaches, which integrate national values, oral folklore, traditional songs, maqom, and contemporary musical genres. The integration of national musical heritage into the educational process not only develops students' musical taste but also instills respect for the cultural heritage of their people. For instance, incorporating folk songs, children's folklore, and performances on national instruments into lessons strengthens students' interest in music. Likewise, the use of maqom, ashula, and lapar expands students' aesthetic thinking and acquaints them with the rich layers of national musical culture. The integrative approach manifests itself not only in music lessons but also in connection with other subjects. For example, performing poetry to melody in literature classes, providing information about renowned composers and musical movements in history lessons, or teaching elements of traditional instrument-making in technology classes all broaden the scope of music education. Evidently, Uzbekistan's educational system is developing new pedagogical concepts by effectively utilizing international experience and harmonizing it with national values. This, in turn, contributes to shaping the aesthetic worldview of the younger generation, developing their creative abilities, and establishing organic links between national and global cultures. Foreign scholars such as T. Suzuki, J. Curwen, É. Jaques-Dalcroze, C. Orff, L. Wyatt, and J. Watson have conducted research on cultivating musical taste in young children, developing creative abilities through audio-visual materials and dramatization, and enhancing emotional responsiveness through interactive activities. Their works provide a scientific basis for modernizing the pedagogical process, implementing methodological

innovations, and fostering students' individual abilities. It is noteworthy that in international practice, creative methods such as games, musical galaxies, interactive exercises, variation techniques, and finger methodologies are widely used in introducing children to musical culture. These methods not only cultivate technical skills but also enhance students' aesthetic sensitivity, musical interest, and creative activity.

Globally, the methodologies for developing musical culture have been widely studied, and they serve as an essential scientific source for enriching Uzbekistan's pedagogical practice, implementing advanced experiences, and effectively developing students' creative and musical abilities. Therefore, studying the outcomes of research conducted in this domain and adapting them to the national education system is considered a pressing task.

The main scientific research directions within this topic can be summarized as follows:

In Uzbekistan, a number of scholars have conducted research on improving the methodology of developing musical culture among primary school students. Among them are Sh. Ayxodjaeva, A. Bakhriyev, G. Ergasheva, D. Kavilova, N.S. Kiyamov, O. Ibrokhimov, H. Nurmatov, Q. Panjiev, R. Qodirov, I. Rajabov, D.Yu. Saipova, N. Khalilov, R. Yunusov, and others. Their studies emphasize the importance of methodological and pedagogical analysis in the process of music education, the ways of developing students' creative activity, and enhancing the effectiveness of methodological approaches in classroom practice. In the CIS countries, a number of prominent scholars have also contributed to this field, including B. Asafyev, V.K. Belabardova, Yu. Borev, L. Dmitriyev, D. Kabalevsky, V. Kanikovskiy, V. Karktechan, S. Karueva, N. Kirilova, M. Klimov, M. Kogan, N. Layzerov, A. Losev, V. Morozov, V.I. Petrushin, V. Sokolov, B. Vasilyev, K. Vinogradov, N.A. Vetlugina, and R. Yusson. Their research focuses on elucidating the theoretical foundations of musical culture development, improving pedagogical methods, and analyzing the processes of fostering musical taste and creative abilities in students. Within their academic legacy, innovative approaches to organizing the process of music education, mechanisms for introducing methodological innovations into practice, and systematic theoretical perspectives are thoroughly substantiated.

Abroad, scholars such as T. Suzuki, J. Curwen, E. Jaques-Dalcroze, C. Orff, L. Wyatt, and J. Watson have conducted research on developing musical taste in young children, applying interactive and creative methods, and fostering musical abilities through audiovisual materials and dramatization. Their works are pedagogically and technologically advanced, creating a foundation for enriching the educational process with innovative approaches.

Achievements in World Science

Interactive methods: Developing students' musical abilities through online platforms, electronic textbooks, games, and simulations.

Creative approaches: Enhancing students' aesthetic taste and creative activity through dramatization, improvisation, and creative exercises.

Pedagogical technologies: Practical application of audiovisual resources, variable learning modules, the finger method, vibrato, and variation techniques.

Competitor Analysis

At present, competitors in the field of music education mainly operate in the following areas:

Developing electronic methodological systems and mobile applications, such as musical games and interactive exercises;

Modernizing pedagogical methods and testing innovative approaches;

Introducing individual and differentiated approaches in music lessons.

The results of the study show that there is a sufficient scientific basis for improving the methodology of developing musical culture in Uzbekistan's education system. However, opportunities for widespread use of interactive methods and innovative pedagogical technologies have not yet been fully realized. Therefore, assimilating the experience of the world and CIS, applying advanced methodological approaches, and modernizing the educational process are considered urgent tasks.

During the research, a new concept will be developed to improve the methodology of fostering musical culture in Uzbekistan's education system. This concept includes interactive and individual approaches as well as the use of modern technologies. It will serve as both a theoretical and practical basis for revealing students' creative abilities, nurturing them in an aesthetic spirit, and strengthening national and cultural values. According to the research results, improving the methodology of developing musical culture in the education system will yield the following outcomes:

Development of Students' Creative and Musical Abilities

Through the implementation of interactive and individualized approaches, variable learning modules, and electronic methodological systems, the musical taste, aesthetic enjoyment, and creative activity of primary school students can be significantly enhanced. In particular, musical-improvisational exercises, listening to and analyzing music of different genres help develop children's auditory memory, rhythmic sensitivity, and creative skills.

1. **Effective Organization of the Learning Process** Incorporating performance techniques such as the finger method, vibrato, variation, and others into music education makes lessons more engaging and interactive. This reduces monotony in the classroom, increases students' interest and motivation toward learning, and as a result, students begin to master music not only by listening but also through practical performance activities.

2. **Improving Pedagogical Practice**, The introduction of methodological manuals, electronic resources, musical galaxy games, and virtual laboratories designed for teachers optimizes the pedagogical process. This not only increases the effectiveness of lessons but also expands the teacher's methodological arsenal, allowing them to carry out pedagogical activities in line with modern requirements.

3. **Applying Innovative Approaches**, the use of audio-visual materials,

dramatization, musical quizzes, and interactive games enhances students' emotional responsiveness. As a result, they perceive music not only as theoretical knowledge but also as an emotional experience. This nurtures their love for music, enriches their aesthetic worldview, and strengthens their inclination toward creativity.

4. Integrating National and International Experience By adopting methodological approaches developed on the basis of CIS countries and international practices, the methodological foundation of Uzbekistan's education system is enriched. In this process, integrating the national traditional musical heritage with advanced foreign technologies plays an important role. Consequently, musical education achieves a synthesis of Uzbek national values and the achievements of global music pedagogy.

Conclusion. Enhancing the quality of music education not only contributes to the improvement of teaching outcomes but also plays a significant role in educating the younger generation in the spirit of national and universal cultural values, fostering their aesthetic taste and creative abilities. Within the educational system of Uzbekistan, this research serves to develop a new methodological concept for advancing the musical culture of youth, introducing interactive and innovative methods, and enhancing the overall quality of the pedagogical process.

As a result, young learners will have broader opportunities to refine their aesthetic perception, creative capacity, and to enrich the cultural environment of society. Moreover, the outcomes of the project create conditions for the systematic development of students' musical hearing, rhythmic sense, intonation, and performance skills. Through the integration of interactive and electronic methodological systems, variable learning modules, and musical games, the teaching process becomes more engaging and effective.

This, in turn, expands opportunities for self-expression, stimulates musical imagination, and enhances creative performance skills. Furthermore, the newly developed methodological approaches, based on pedagogical experiments, provide teachers with concrete recommendations for organizing lessons through individualized and differentiated approaches. At the same time, adapting advanced international practices to the educational context of Uzbekistan significantly increases the effectiveness of the pedagogical process.

ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI | СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ | REFERENCES

1. Ergasheva, Ch. E. (2020). Issues of the history and theory of music in the treatises of Eastern scholars. In Proceedings of the 3rd International Scientific-Practical Conference on the Issues of Art and Musical Culture in the Historical Heritage of Medieval Eastern Scholars and Thinkers (p. 162). Tashkent.
2. Fitrat, A. (1993). Uzbek classical music and its history. Tashkent: Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Fan Publishing House.
3. Frank, S. L. (1997). Reality of man. Thinkers of the 20th century. Moscow: Respublika.

4. Ginecinskiy, V. I. (1991). Individualization as a subject of pedagogical anthropology. *Soviet Pedagogy*, (9), 46–49.
5. Ginzburg, M. R. (1994). The psychological content of personal self-determination. *Questions of Psychology*, (3), 43–53.
6. Igamova, D. N., & Mamatova, N. A. (2019). Games in the education. *Problems of Pedagogy*, 2(41).
7. International Society for Contemporary Music (ISCM). (2021). History summary: Toward a global community: The history of the International Society for Contemporary Music 1933–2021 (R. Murray Schafer, Ed.).
8. Isoqov, Z. (2019). Attention to art and culture in Uzbekistan as the main criterion of social reforms. *Bulletin of the State Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan*, 3(11), 9–17.
9. Isroilova, S. (2013). Stylistic tendencies in the development of Uzbek choral music in the 1970–1990s (Candidate of Arts dissertation). Tashkent.
10. Kavilova, D. A. (n.d.). Development of musical-creative abilities in university students (PhD dissertation).
11. Kiyamov, N. S. (2019). Pedagogical foundations of improving musical culture among university students (Doctoral dissertation). Tashkent.
12. Klobukova, N. F. (2018). Western musical culture in Japan during the Meiji period (1868–1912): Borrowing and adaptation (Abstract of Candidate of Cultural Studies dissertation). Moscow.
13. Mardonov, Sh. (2006). Training and improving the qualifications of pedagogical personnel based on new educational values. Tashkent: Fan.
14. Matyakubov, I. (2020). The use of multimedia tools in developing the creative abilities of future music teachers. *Public Education Journal*, (2), 82–85.
15. Safarova, R. (2003). Some issues of transition to differentiated education. In *Proceedings of the Republican Scientific-Practical Conference* (pp. 124–127). Tashkent.
16. Saliyeva, Z. T. (2017). Improving mechanisms for developing the spiritual culture of students in pedagogical higher education institutions (Doctoral dissertation). Tashkent.
17. Saipova, D. Yu. (2019). Theory and methodology of music teaching.
18. Yarmatov, R. B. (2017). Improving the pedagogical mechanisms of educating and developing gifted students (PhD dissertation). Tashkent

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